

Article: **AFFECTIVE LEARNING STUDYING THE INFLUENCE OF POSITIVE EMOTIONS ON LEARNING**

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AFFECTIVE LEARNING STUDYING THE INFLUENCE OF POSITIVE EMOTIONS ON LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the academic emotions experienced by students, with a particular emphasis on their affective states concerning acquiring knowledge, pedagogical methods, and attainment of goals. The positive emotions on the achievement of desired educational outcomes and identify circumstances that elicit positive affect. Although an excess of negativity poses an impediment to progress, moderate levels of anxiety or perplexity, when accompanied by self-assurance, can exert beneficial influence on attainment of educational objectives. The investigation examines the presence of positive emotions in context of learning and teaching, which is an area that has received limited attention in the past. Employing a novel method for measuring emotions, the study examines interview data obtained from 36 individuals who volunteered to participate in the research at an Australian university. The analysis delves into various themes associated with five positive emotions, thus facilitating a comparison of viewpoints between students and lecturers.

Keywords: Positive emotions, Affective learning, educational psychology, Emotional regulation, Motivation, Student-teacher relationships.

Introduction:

Positive emotions play vital and basic role in human behavior and adjustment. They facilitate the visualization of objectives and challenges, stimulate cognitive processes and problem-solving abilities, promote well-being by enhancing resilience, foster meaningful connections with important individuals, establish the foundation for personal self-regulation, and shape the conduct of collectives, social systems, and nations. Despite the manifold functions they serve, positive emotions have been overlooked by the field of psychology. Until recently, the focus of psychology has predominantly centered on the darker aspects of human existence. Psychopathological conduct, negative emotions arising from stress, and the management of stress and negative emotions have been extensively investigated, whereas adaptive conduct, positive emotions, and proactive coping strategies have not received commensurate attention.¹

The conventional theories that address the functions of positive emotions in cognition and behavior have primarily focused on the negative consequences of positive emotions, rather than recognizing their regulatory benefits. The field of education holds particular significance in shaping human self-regulation and development, with the positive emotions of both students and teachers assumed to play a central role in achieving

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educational objectives. However, educational psychology and research have also overlooked positive emotions, despite their importance. While there has been extensive examination of students' test anxiety, there has been limited analysis of positive emotions related to learning and achievement. This is surprising considering that traditional theories of achievement motivation have identified anticipatory hope and pride, along with anticipatory fear and shame, as key factors influencing motivation and task behavior.²

Studies on achievement motivation have included items related to these emotions in overall assessments of achievement motives, but the emotions themselves have rarely been the focus of investigation. Specifically, this applies to the positive emotions of hope and pride, which have only been considered as components of the motive to achieve success. On the other hand, the motive to avoid failure has been equated with test anxiety at an operational level, often assessed through test anxiety questionnaires in numerous studies.³

Negative emotions, which are perceived as unpleasant, can elicit a spectrum of physiological and cognitive responses. Exemplars of active and potential negative emotions encompass anxiety effects, anger, and shameful act, whereas hopelessness and boredom are deemed as deactivating negative emotions.⁴

The negative emotions express a substituent impact on the learning and getting education process of domain. It impacts a great effect on stunted attentional allocation, motivation and energetic employment of learning and skills strategies with the his or her own educating stability with regulatory effects. Apart from irrelevancy undertaken emotions, lack of attentions, can manipulate the learner abilities from vital directions. For that sake the anxiety and mental negative thoughts can lead a person from basic and necessary route to diverted one which cause to destruction of objects and objects. while boredom can instigate daydreaming and a lack of engagement. With respect to motivation, with respect to motivation, actively working of negative emotions such as anxiety and shame may diminish profit and internal motivation. Opposite this, reducing the negative emotional feelings in example to having no hope or positive signature towards natural phenomena and boredom generally block the learning signals.⁵

As for learning strategies, activating negative emotions may engender the application of strictly learning strategies, such as simple memorization. Oppositely, reducing the negative emotions may result in a lack of strategic utilization and superficial processing of information. Regarding self-regulation of learning, negative emotions can impede a student's ability to use flexible thinking and self-regulation, potentially leading to increased reliance on external guidance, such as teachers and parents. In the classroom, negative emotions can impede students' learning progress, leading to avoidance behaviors, procrastination, exam failure, and even dropouts. It is crucial to assist students in preventing and alleviating excessive negative academic emotions. However, it is also important to recognize that some level of negative emotions can be productive if managed appropriately. Mild forms of anxiety, self-related anger, or shame, when coupled with confidence in success, can actually augment learning. Similarly, a certain

level of confusion regarding cognitive problems can facilitate conceptual change and the development of sophisticated knowledge structures.⁶

To foster a productive classroom culture, educators should focus on enhancing students' confidence in problem-solving abilities, encouraging mastery of learning material, and re-conceptualizing errors as opportunities for growth and learning. The aim is to minimize excessive negative emotions in students while creating an environment that harnesses the energy provided by unpleasant emotions to enhance learning. This objective can be achieved through a combination of preventive measures and appropriate management of negative emotions.⁷

Methodology:

The main purpose and objective of the current era was to comprehensively and critically analysis and delve into the perceptions and perspectives of university students and educators regarding positive emotions within the context of the learning environment. To attain this ambitious goal, the researchers opted to employ a cutting-edge and innovative prototype approach, which is characterized by the utilization of mental representations of emotion categories. This approach was employed in order to effectively comprehend and gain insights into the ways in which emotions are perceived, labeled, and ultimately experienced. It is worth mentioning that this remarkable and groundbreaking approach considers emotions as being able to be categorized along a positive-negative dimension, as well as across discrete and diverse emotion categories, such as interest and enjoyment.

The particularly approach, which can be used for analytical research work is comprehensively used in middle ground in tween the subdivisonal type of dimensional approach; when it expresses to organizing the emotional activities. Apart from all these reality facts, that it is generate the extensively coordination and validation from past empirically analysis for any study work. It is important to note down that's why piratically application in learning and educational validity is still not fully available. That's why the researcher who belongs to scientific or analytical approach to reduce the gap of critically analytical skills by using the prototype analysis to analysis and scrutinize emotions concept that are transfer from first generation to next generations with learning attitude.

The central information regarding to this study was to basically approach the analytical thoughts towards the questions that the give an idea to researcher about effectiveness of study and comprehensively work.

Firstly, the researchers endeavored to meticulously explore and investigate the impact and influence of positive emotions on various learning outcomes based on the perceptions and opinions of the participants. Secondly, they sought to investigate and expose the various domains of learning fields that are inherently linked with eliciting positive emotions. It is important to note that the larger research project, of which this study is an integral part, encompasses and encompasses various emotions that are experienced during tertiary learning. However, the main focus of this study was to

comprehensively understand and gain insights into the causes and consequences of positive emotions within the intricate and complex learning process.

The analytical process towards the enrolled total of thirty-six (36), volunteer and all they were directly affiliated with and reputed Australian University under the umbrella of Sydney. All the people who take part in this study, all were divided into dual bilateral symmetry, with given name 21 university students and 15 technical delivering community. Those who were learner in academia only 14 were females and 7 males took participate in that activity. The sample of all the enrolled people was diversified and huge range was enclosed in it. This scientific approach was used to entertained the exploration of emotions and education from abroad perspective. While to keep it confidential all the people were assignments pseudonyms.

To evaluate the emotional experiences of the participants, the researchers opted for in-depth interviews which are a commonly employed technique used to assess subjective emotional experiences. During the interviews, the volunteers were requested to recollect specific emotional experiences tied to their learning process and were subsequently interrogated about their assessment of these experiences. The question which was asked during interview, formulated researchers based on a comprehensive review of the existing literature study were supplied with the insights from old study level. The questions were semi-structured in nature and allowed the participants to share their positive emotional experiences in a type of learning contexts, including feedback and assessment, by own regulatory emotions and interactions between students and teachers. Although both staff and students were asked similar questions, the wording was adjusted to be contextually relevant. In cases where the initial questions did not elicit detailed responses, probes were used. The interviews were conducted for a duration of 30 to 60 minutes each.

Results:

In order to decipher and scrutinize the interview data, the QSR NVivo 9 software was utilized to encode and dissect the transcripts. The encoding of emotions was based on prototype theory, which entailed the categorization and organization of the emotions that were articulated by the participants. A collection of different types and different directional trend was adopted in the measurement of emotions, with the hierarchical organization of vital emotions directions primarily following the model suggested by Shaver et al. Initially, emotions were encoded using the participants' own lexicon, whereby those that referred to individual traits or behaviors were eliminated. Subsequently, the emotions were grouped into either positive or negative categories, based on the dimensional approach. Further classification of discrete positive emotions was accomplished using a categorical approach, where they were grouped under the umbrella of five "*vital emotions directions*" namely happened and joyful, interest taking activity, loveable, and self-handling emotions feelings.

The qualitative encoding was utilized to encode the themes that emerged from the data. This method facilitated the identification and scrutiny of patterns and themes that were

discernible within the responses. Various encoding techniques, such as elemental, thematic, process, and in vivo encoding, were employed in selection of topics and compile a comprehensive list of situations and themes that could be linked to each emotion dimension. The codes and themes were evaluated and refined in order to generate a smaller set of huge range of themes and substituent themes. This procedure was in line with the methodology outlined in Braun and Clarke's work, hence the representative data of individual theme was recognized in relationship with theme codes.

Table: 1 In analyzing and comprehensively unraveling the intricacies of the interview process, it is imperative to cognitively process and critically evaluate the key questions that are paramount for each specific theme in order to effectively elicit the necessary information that is pertinent to the overall objective of the interview. These queries should be tailored and individualized to suit the unique requirements of the particular theme at hand, in order to optimally extract the most relevant and salient information that is paramount for the successful accomplishment of the interviewee's objectives.

Subject matters	Scholars	Lecturers
Feelings Index	Which emotional attachment do you consider important to you in the learning process?	Which emotions index do you consider are noteworthy in the learning process?
Zeal Energy	Describe a time when you felt excited about a subject. What made it exciting for you?	How do you foster a sense of interest or zeal energy source in your students?
Emotional state spectrum	Revised the thoughts of depression and anxiety? How did you manage your emotions to successfully complete your tasks?	What strategies do you think are crucial for students to cope with emotional stress and stay focused on their work?

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Motivation	What factors motivate you to learn and engage in your studies?	From your perspective, what motivates students to be actively involved in their learning?
Relationships	Do you feel you have sufficient personal interaction with your teachers?	Do you believe students receive enough personalized contact with academic persons?
Assessment	How do you feel when you assess feedback on your academic performance?	What are students' typical reactions to self-assessment?
Perspective on others	How do you feel teaching staff view students? Are they empathetic towards student concerns?	How do you perceive students' attitudes towards teaching staff? Are they understanding of lecturers?

Invitations were extended to a multitude of individuals, encompassing both students and staff from a diverse range of faculties, through the medium of electronic mail in order to partake according to this study. The dual beyond to dependent assistant, were responsible for conducting interviews on the university premises. As a token of our appreciation for their valuable time and contribution, each participant was remunerated with a movie ticket. As a means of ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the data, the conducted interview and session was kept in saved mode while recording it, further it was transcribed by the officials.

Effectiveness of optimistic emotions

The present study aims to explicate the absorbed the influence of the pessimistic feelings, positive emotions on learning, and the participants' views on the same were explored in detail. In order to derive a well-defined and detailed knowledge of influence of the positive emotions on learning, participants' responses were cross-referenced with cognitive and non-cognitive categories using matrix coding queries. The study found that positive emotions had a significant positive impact on three master areas of functioning, namely cognitive and social practical applications, motivation, and self-efficacy, coping, and resilience. Positive emotions were highlighted to upgrade the ability to memorize the

things, focus on target, and communication skills with social network. While abrupt emotions, particularly fear, were viewed as potential obstacles. Furthermore, positively optimistic emotions were linked with connected approach action-tendencies and behaviors, motivating students to engage actively in their studies. However, some participants noted that a certain level of anxiety or "intensity" was necessary for optimal learning, as overly positive emotions could lead to complacency. The study also found that positive emotions, such as joy/happiness and pride, were linked to increased self-efficacy, and they played a crucial role in coping and resilience, helping students "bounce back" after facing challenges.

Origin of optimistic educations.

In order to communicate with the runner-up research query on the sources of positive emotions in learning, coding categories were grouped into three broad themes: owing the passionate query, social circular environment, and individual fluctuating. An individual owing zealous exploration refers to students' genuine interest and excitement about a particular subject, which motivates them to enroll in related courses and engage with the material. The social environment, including interactions with teachers and classmates, was also identified as a source of pessimistic feelings in the learning process. In the last a person individual or group work may have personal properties towards participating or learning. All these are recognized as critically point which add and impact on inflicting the experience of pessimistic emotionalist learning attachment in the book. This is reason educational or practical activity gives and extensively undertesting of the act in fruitfully emotions while learnings. Positive feelings such a delightful thoughts and ideas add great impact on fruitful result for any task work. The positive or negative thoughts or g emotional feelings have direct link with the result of research work, daily task or learning behavior in class room. With this explanation these emotional attachment with learning room is important for people then people engaged passionate and energetics.

Passionate working in educational institute of field is directly correlate with the extra curriculum activity and methodology they are following to.

In regards to relevant curricula, when students find course topics, content, and materials that are relatable to their real-life experiences and career aspirations, they experience heightened feelings of interest and excitement. For example, a student pursuing a career as an art teacher may feel enthusiastic about an art history course. Lecturers recognize the importance of developing curricula that students find enjoyable and stimulating. They aim to make the theoretical aspects of the curriculum applicable to real life through experiential learning, thus fostering interest and enjoyment in the subject matter. The availability of cooperative excitement in-between learning students and material delivering community for a particular objective domain which take part to upgrade the happiness of learning and pessimistic feelings. Student usually utilize to them with a specific nae as *love* to explain their deep affectionate towards the goal or subjects.

Apart from the be a part of delivering the knowledge, the mode of translocate of educational material which also include the academic person personal personality, ethics

and way how he or she provide the information, having a great influx on creating the interesting attention and excited state of students towards learning. All the students' thoughts that "*expert delivery methodology*" should be essential part of academic activity especially when the reading material is not as much interested for students, this will help them to engage into learning activities. Internal feelings entertain as the corridor for interconnecting the students with teacher, this will make easy to digest the reading material for students leading to understand. Delivery methodology, teaching ethics, and expertise in domain have great impact to engage the students in study.

Humor is a frequently cited strategy employed by lecturers to generate positive emotions and promote engagement. Students also feel a sense of reciprocity, feeling obligated to reciprocate the energy invested by the lecturers.

In terms of genuine emotion, while enthusiastic delivery is essential, the emotion expressed by the lecturers must be genuine to engage students fully. Students value teachers who genuinely enjoy and are excited about teaching their discipline. Love and appreciation are felt by students when they perceive teachers' emotions as authentic, and they are less receptive when teachers' fake emotion. Lecturers acknowledge that students are perceptive and can recognize fake enthusiasm.

Lecturers recognize the importance of modeling genuine emotions, understanding that it requires expertise and competence. Fear of appearing incompetent is identified as a potential barrier to student engagement, contrasting with the excitement associated with being competent.

The passionate inquiry involves curricula that resonate with students required an interesting and valuable with fruits learnings, delivered by genuinely engaged teaching staff. Positive emotions play a crucial role in enhancing cognitive and communicable with socially active functioning, motivational facts, self-efficacy, coping, and resilience in educational contexts.

Summary of key findings.

Fig 2: source of positive information and its impacts

Discussion:

The outcomes of the present investigation furnish significant insights into the ramifications of positive emotions on learning. The results bring to the fore the paramountcy of positive emotions in augmenting cognitive and social functioning, motivation, and self-efficacy in educational settings. However, further research is indispensable to address the limitations of the study and scrutinize the role of negative emotions in these contexts.⁸

The conventional theories that address the cognitive and behavioral functions of positive emotions have primarily focused on the adverse effects of these emotions, rather than their beneficial regulatory effects. Educational settings play a crucial role in shaping human self-regulation and development, where the positive emotions of both students and teachers are assumed to be central in achieving educational goals. However, educational psychology and research have also neglected positive emotions, despite the extensive study of students' test anxiety and the limited analysis of positive emotions related to learning and achievement. This neglect is surprising considering that traditional theories of achievement motivation have identified anticipatory hope and pride, in addition to fear and shame, as key determinants of motivation and task behavior.⁹

So far, psychology and educational research have failed to consider the positive dimension of human emotions. An implicit assumption underlying this neglect suggests that positive emotions are less important for theoretical explanations and practical applications of human behavior compared to negative emotions.¹⁰ In this context, we argue that positive emotions are no less essential than negative affect. We discuss the theoretical assumptions and empirical findings of our studies on students' educational emotions, focusing on the occurrence, magnitude, consequences, and triggers of positive emotions.

The control-value theory can provide a theoretical foundation for designing interventions and classroom instructions that promote positive emotions among students. These interventions can target the appraisals that underlie students' emotions, as well as the instructional and social environments that influence these appraisals and emotions. With regard to appraisals, the theory suggests that interventions that enhance students' sense of control and values are particularly important. For example, reattribution training can help students develop a sense of control over subjective outcomes by altering their causal attributions of success and failure. Such training can be implemented on an individual basis or integrated into regular classroom instruction.¹¹ Improving the quality of instruction and fostering enthusiastic engagement in teaching can also be effective methods. Additionally, granting students autonomy in regulating their own learning, creating academic cultures that embrace learning from mistakes and view them as opportunities for improvement rather than as grounds for punishment, can reduce negative emotions and lay the foundation for positive affective experiences even in cases of non-mastery. Finally, establishing strong connections with students can facilitate the transmission of positive academic values and the maintenance of a mastery-oriented climate that prevents the development of anti-achievement norms prevalent in many classrooms today.¹²

The scientific research results significantly promote those emotions activity that influence the momentous phenomena to enhance the social role, positive vibes and self-creating road map. The students exposed the pessimistic emotionally feelings, for example happiness and excited moments, with full of energetic feelings.¹³

Conclusion:

The conventional theories that address the cognitive and behavioral functions of positive emotions have primarily focused on the negative consequences of positive emotions, rather than their regulatory advantages. This is surprising, considering that traditional theories of achievement motivation have regarded anticipatory hope and pride in relation to success and failure as key factors influencing motivation and task behavior, along with anticipatory fear and shame.¹⁴ One implicit assumption underlying this neglect is that positive emotions of high quality are less important for theoretical explanations of human functioning and their practical applications compared to negative emotions.¹⁵ The findings suggest that students experience a wide range of positive emotions in academic settings while attending classes, studying, and taking tests and exams.¹⁶ One implication of these findings is that there are multiple ways to foster positive emotions in students by addressing individual appraisals or academic antecedents that induce such emotions.¹⁷

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